

Expansion of the Toulouse Task Force on ISRU activities: indirect additive manufacturing with FFF

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Introduction: With the progress of the Artemis program, which aims to return humans to the Moon, particularly with the second mission scheduled for early this year, the development of In Situ Resources Utilization technologies is more relevant than ever.

In previous editions [1-4], the Toulouse Taskforce on ISRU presented its progress on the development of an analogue of lunar regolith, called BPY (Basalt of Pic d'Ysson). This had the distinctive feature of having a customizable composition, through the addition of oxides and amorphous material, allowing it to cover the variability of lunar regolith in terms of chemical composition and maturity. This manufacturing method offers numerous advantages: reduced payload, possibility of using solar radiation as an energy source, adaptability to objects of various sizes, etc.

This analog was then characterized physically in terms of its optical and thermal properties, and finally used in direct additive manufacturing operations using Selective Laser Melting [5]. This manufacturing method offered numerous advantages: reduced payload, the possibility of using solar radiation as an energy source, and adaptability to objects of various sizes, etc.

For this fifth consecutive edition, the Toulouse Taskforce is expanding its field of study by presenting its work on indirect additive manufacturing using Fused Filament Fabrication, still using the same starting material, BPY. This new method complements the first one, using a fine particle size range independent of previous tests, as shown in Figure 1. The presentation will outline the various major stages of this manufacturing process, from printing to consolidation by sintering.

Fig 1: Particle size distribution of the BPY analog determined by laser diffraction granulometry, before and after sieving

Filament properties and printing step: The print quality of a part produced using FFF depends primarily on the properties of its filament. Its composition, divided into chemical binder, “backbone” binder, and ceramic filler (BPY), is analyzed using microscopic observations, thermal analysis tools (ATD, DSC) and X-ray diffraction (XRD). The amount of analog in the filament, estimated at 60% in volume, is satisfactory in a lunar base context where the supply of organic material remains complex, as this value exceeds the usual loads listed in recent literature [6]. The filament itself can then be characterized in terms of temperature by analyzing its rheology: in a printing context, a viscosity that is low enough to obtain a constant nozzle output flow, yet high enough to ensure continuous flow, is desired and researched. Figure 2 shows an example of a part produced at a slightly too high temperature, resulting in burrs.

Fig 2: photograph of a first FFF printing trial with a BPY filament, exhibiting overextrusion defects

A second aspect to consider is the machine settings, printing strategy and more generally the environment surrounding the printing process: the choice of adequate printing speed, flow rates, layer height, nozzle distance from the working surface, and the impact of the object geometry (presence of negative slopes and bridges, number of walls, filling pattern...) are discussed.

Debinding and consolidation: Once printed, the part must typically undergo three post-processing steps: chemical debinding and thermal debinding, followed by a sintering phase. The optimal post-treatment protocol is discussed: it consists of debinding the part in acetone for 48 hours, then it is moved into an oven where its temperature is slowly raised at 600°C for

thermal debinding during one hour, immediately followed by a 2° C/min raise until 1135°C where the part will sinter during 1h30, followed by a cooling step at 2°C/min. The result of such a treatment is shown in Figure 3.

Fig 3: (left) example of a debinded and sintered FFF sample, and (right)

The microstructure, including porosity and phases present, is once again analyzed using optical microscope and SEM observations, as well as EDS spot measurements and mapping. The output objects have a high density of around 90%, with crystalline phases faithful to the original basalt: the presence of iron oxides such as ilmenite and magnetite, pyroxenes such as diopside, and olivines such as forsterite is observed within a plagioclase-type matrix. The amorphous or crystalline nature of this matrix remains to be confirmed, either by XRD on a section or by electron diffraction on a thin sample. The impact of such a microstructure on mechanical properties (hardness, compressive strength) will be discussed.

Conclusion and prospects: In a subsequent stage, this process will be redesigned to be more effectively adapted to the context of a lunar base. illustrated in figure 4. In a subsequent stage, this process will be redesigned to be more effectively adapted to the context of a lunar base. The filament used to date, composed of commercial organic binders with the assistance of the French company 3D Ceram, will be compared with a new one using PHBV-type biopolymer. In a subsequent stage, this process will be redesigned to be more effectively adapted to the context of a lunar base. The filament used to date, composed of commercial organic binders with the assistance of the French company 3D Ceram, will be compared with a new one using PHBV-type biopolymers. These are the subject of study by partners at the Toulouse Biotechnology Institute, who are seeking to produce them bacteriologically from astronauts' waste, in a closed-loop system designed to reduce payload. In line with this approach, the chemical debinding phase will be omitted, eliminating a step in the process and removing the need to transport a solvent such as acetone.

Finally, there will be an overview of the task force's efforts to predict the future of ISRU manufacturing, through collaborations carried out since the second edition of the workshop held at the Cité de l'Espace in Toulouse in April 2025, as shown in Figure 4. In particular, emphasis will be placed on the need for standardization of testing in the European research environment and the establishment of specifications and a common quality approach.

Fig 4: Participants of the 2nd Toulouse Task Force's workshop on ISRU (10th April 2025)

References: [1-4] Granier J. et al. , ELS 2022-2025, In-Situ Resource Utilization. [5] Granier J. et al, Acta Astronautica 226 (2025) 66–77. [6] S. Moazen et al, Acta Astronautica, 2025